

An interconnected modular setup for in-vivo evaluation of automated mechanical ventilation

V. Pfannschmidt^{1*}, M. Buglowski¹, M. Grüne¹, F. Hammer¹, O. Braun³, M. Hütten⁴, S. Kowalewski¹, M. Schoberer², and A. Stollenwerk¹

¹ Embedded Software (Informatik 11), RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany

² Neonatology Section of the Department of Paediatric and Adolescent Medicine, RWTH Aachen University Hospital, Aachen, Germany

³ Löwenstein Medical SE & Co. KG, Bad Ems, Germany

⁴ Department of Pediatrics, School of Oncology and Developmental Biology (GROW), Maastricht University, Maastricht, The Netherlands)

* Corresponding author, email: pfannschmidt@embedded.rwth-aachen.de

Abstract: In-vivo evaluation of automated mechanical ventilation requires not only the reliable interconnection of medical devices but also combined efforts of experts from the medical and technical field. We present a setup for the in-vivo evaluation of automated ventilation of neonates. An application running on a laptop integrates measurements from several devices and executes the ventilation controller. Ventilation measurements are processed in real-time using a microcontroller node. A dedicated GUI allows for operation of the setup by clinicians and engineers. The setup was successfully applied for automatic ventilation of preterm lambs.

© Copyright 2024

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License CC-BY 4.0., which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

I. Introduction

Mechanical ventilation of preterm neonates requires tight regulation of the arterial partial pressure of carbon dioxide (PaCO₂). Today, this task is performed by clinicians, demanding not only a high level of experience and attention, but also time. Automatic control of PaCO₂ in a Physiological Closed-Loop Control (PCLC) setting has the potential to relieve medical staff and monitor and adjust ventilation in a continuous fashion, which could improve patient care compared to manual control. Developing such a PCLC system requires an interdisciplinary team of technical and medical experts. Special attention must be paid to the evaluation to ensure patient safety. We developed a system for automatic control of PaCO₂ in preterm neonates and presented first results in a preterm lamb model [1,2]. To enable in-vivo evaluation an interconnected setup was developed, which we present here.

A previously described setup for the evaluation of automated mechanical ventilation of adults uses a real-time PC for executing the control algorithm being connected to a medical panel PC for visualization [3]. A decentralized setup for the automated perfusion of kidney grafts was presented in [4]. This setup makes use of the self-developed and openly available ASMO board [5,6], a microcontroller board specifically designed for the interconnection of medical devices.

In this work we will present our interconnected setup for evaluating the automated ventilation of neonates which is unique in three ways. First, the setup combines an ordinary laptop executing the control algorithm with a microcontroller node for real-time communication. Second, a Near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS) device is included, which communicates

with the laptop over the air. Third, a custom control app was developed, which manages the data flow and provides a GUI to allow monitoring and configuration of the controller and medical devices by technical and medical personnel.

II. Interconnected setup

In our setup, shown in Figure 1, a laptop running Windows 10 is used to execute our control app, which integrates the data streams sent from several devices, executes the PaCO₂ controller, and sends the control settings to the ventilator.

Figure 1: Scheme of the interconnected ventilation setup. Solid lines indicate wired connections, whereas dashed lines indicate connections over the air.

Given our controller operates on high-level ventilation settings and leaves the timing and control of single breaths to the ventilator [1,2], no real-time operating system is necessary. Having the computational power of a laptop available allows for future extendibility with more complex algorithms, e.g. using machine learning or optimization-based control.

A LeoniPlus (Löwenstein Medical SE & Co. KG, Germany) neonatal ventilator is used to ventilate newborn lambs. The device was adjusted by the manufacturer to accept settings via an RS-232 interface. Ventilation measurements are provided by the ventilator using a proprietary serial protocol and include flow, pressure, oxygen saturation, the concentration of CO₂ taken by a proximal mainstream sensor (MASIMO IRMA CO₂, Masimo Corporation, USA), and values processed by the ventilator. These data are received in real-time by the microcontroller node, for which an ASMO board is used, through an RS-232 interface. From the microcontroller node the data are passed on to the control app for further processing and logging using a Controller Area Network (CAN) bus. The serial protocol used by the ventilator is the only hard real-time constraint in the setup. Further real-time requirements as well as further sensors or actuators may be handled by additional microcontroller nodes interconnected via CAN [5,6]. Vital parameter recordings include subcutaneous needle electrode electrocardiography and invasive blood pressure. Vital parameters are processed and displayed by a patient monitor (Philips DACH GmbH, Germany) and sent to the control app via Ethernet for logging. A NIRS device (Artinis Medical Systems, The Netherlands) is included to record cerebral blood flow and regional tissue oxygenation. This measurement technique was incorporated to assess potential effects of PaCO₂ control on brain perfusion and oxygenation because unphysiological levels of PaCO₂ are associated with brain injury in preterm neonates [7]. The NIRS device is connected to the control app over the air using Bluetooth.

III. Control app

The control app at the heart of our setup manages signal flow and handles measurements for further processing and logging. The app was implemented in C++ using the Qt 5 Framework (Qt Group Plc, Finland). The controller was implemented in MATLAB SIMULINK (The Mathworks, USA) and integrated into the app as an automatically generated C++ class. Combined use of these tools allows for cross-platform development and rapid prototyping to achieve fast development cycles in an interdisciplinary development

process together with medical experts. The control app's strictly layered architecture, shown in Figure 2, enables modularity, extendibility, and efficient debugging. Measurements received by the app as described in Section II are propagated to the algorithmic functionality, namely the controller, algorithms for the estimation of the control variable PaCO₂, alarming, and logging. Newly created outputs of the algorithms are displayed in the GUI and, in case of the controller, sent to the ventilator. All measurements and outputs are integrated and synchronized by the logging functionality and stored locally on the laptop.

The GUI allows to monitor and configure the controller and the connections to all medical devices. It was designed together with clinicians to be used by an interdisciplinary team. Motivated by the requirements defined by IEC 60601-1-10 [8] the values and curves of the reference variable, controller output variables, and physiological feedback variable are visualized. The app was successfully used by clinicians, computer scientists, and engineers in experiments described before [1,2].

IV. Conclusion

We present a modular setup for automatic ventilation of neonatal lambs. The interconnection of medical devices and data flow is managed by our control app and an microcontroller node for real-time handling of the ventilation data. The GUI facilitates combined development efforts by medical and technical experts.

The setup is created in a modular fashion and can be easily extended to incorporate further devices in the future, e.g. transcutaneous CO₂ monitoring. To enhance in-silico evaluation in the sense of the 3R principle the control app can be connected to a simulated ventilation process.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The NIRS device was provided by Artinis Medical Systems.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

Research funding: This work was supported by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) (Grant 13GW0292). Conflict of interest: Authors state no conflict of interest. Ethical approval: Animal experiments were approved by the Dutch Central Authority for Scientific Procedures on Animals (AVD10700202010347).

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Buglowski et al. *Closed-Loop Control of Arterial CO₂ in Mechanical Ventilation of Neonates* in 2022 44th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC), 2022.
- [2] V. Pfannschmidt et al. *Closed-Loop Control of Arterial CO₂ for Neonatal Mechanical Ventilation: In-Vivo Interaction with Spontaneous Breathing* in IFAC-PapersOnLine, 2024.
- [3] P. von Platen et al. *A rapid control prototyping system for the automated control of mechanical ventilation* in Proc AUTOMED, 2020.
- [4] M. Wiertalla et al. *A fully automated normothermic machine perfusion system for kidney grafts supporting physiological motivated flow profiles* in Current Directions in Biomedical Engineering, 2023.
- [5] F. Berg et al. *ASMO: a decentralized and verifiable interoperability platform in intensive care* in Proc AUTOMED, 2023.
- [6] M. Wiertalla et al. *A modular and verifiable software architecture for interconnected medical systems in intensive care* in Annals of Computer Science and Information Systems, 2023.
- [7] J. Fabres et al. *Both extremes of arterial carbon dioxide pressure and the magnitude of fluctuations in arterial carbon dioxide pressure are associated with severe intraventricular hemorrhage in preterm infants* in Pediatrics, vol. 119, no. 2, pp. 299–305, 2007.
- [8] International Electrotechnical Commission: Medical electrical equipment – Part 1-10: General requirements for basic safety and essential performance – Collateral Standard: Requirements for the development of physiologic closed-loop controllers (IEC 60601-1-10:2007 + A1:2013).

Figure 2: Architecture of the Control App used for in-vivo evaluation of our control algorithm.